

Attracting young talent to aeronautics: Human Resources perspective

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Abstract

According to the Social Cognitive Career Theory (SCCT), the career and/or academic choices of young people are influenced by personal, cognitive and contextual factors and form gradually more consciously from childhood and primary school, through teenage and secondary school to adulthood and university, as proposed by the Life Span, Life Span Theory. Therefore, to attract young talent to the aerospace sector, we may start at an early life stage and always keep in mind the four factors from SCCT that help identify and understand the reasons why students pursue a university course: prior experience, social support, self-efficacy, and outcome expectation. Before choosing what studies to pursue in university, young people need prior experiences in the subject, meaning that we should promote the exposure to aerospace matters before university.

However, it is important to ensure that aeronautics careers are well seen, and human resources practices are crucial for that. When organizations have principles and strategies in order to motivate and retain the workforce, the right image about the sector is constructed and has an impact on attracting young talent after school.

Therefore, young people should be encouraged by their parents, educators, and peers to pursue careers in aerospace and, for this to happen, on the one hand, the numerous careers in the sector should be spread in terms of their variety, characteristics, work conditions, and education needs. On the other hand, the sector should be promoted as technologically advanced, one of the most interdisciplinary branches of engineering, an enabler of a variety of vehicles and, finally, an opportunity to integrate all these technologies in a vehicle that is safe, efficient and environmentally friendly while allowing fast travel to a wide range of destinations, some previously inaccessible. Finally, the fascinating promise of aerospace must be settled in high-quality jobs that give the necessary knowledge, motivation, and conditions to make it memorable and enable that "the word is spread" between young talents.

1. Introduction

The aerospace sector seeks to attract and retain young talent for its future and growth, due to the current global shortfall in the numbers of qualified employees that is imposing huge pressures on employers to recruit the greatest number of qualified employees.

The career inclinations of young people, in general, begin with a range of factors that influence their choices and can form gradually more consciously from childhood and primary school, through teenage and secondary school, to adulthood and university. According to the Social Cognitive Career Theory (SCCT),

the academic and career choices of young people are influenced by several factors and form gradually more consciously from childhood to adulthood.

Despite the obvious importance of changes in curriculum and pedagogies [1], it is important to conceptualize that the idea formed about the aeronautics organizations and about the sector can constitute a critical factor which influence the career choice.

Taking this into account, the focus on a human resources perspective brings an important contribute to understand how some strategies and policies can have influence on attracting young talent to the sector.

Human resources practices are recognized as important elements of business strategy development and they include, for example, recruitment and integration, employee involvement, internal communication, training and reward and commitment. In fact, practices and strategies that motivate and retain the actual workforce, are also essential to attract new workers. More, when organizations follow this concept, the sector itself benefits from the “good reputation” associated.

From employer branding, that attracts the workforce, to the strategies to their stability through retention, there are factors such as organizational culture and satisfaction of employees which constitutes core issues on this theme.

Actually, this kind of practices, with focus on employee and their well-being, that assure the satisfaction, happiness, and loyalty, are exactly the way we can retain workers and attract new personnel, guaranteeing the stability of the workforce and the sustainability of the sector. This, collectively with awareness campaigns to enrich public understanding of career opportunities in Aerospace Sector and their nature, tasks, progression prospects and working conditions, are the two critical steps to attract young people in a Human Resources perspective.

In Aerospace, with the current global shortfall in the numbers of qualified employees, it is not only important to conquer kids at schools and at home (e.g., parents, TV shows, books) but additionally show young talent that, in a possible future, they will be valued, motivated and well-paid in an organization of the sector.

2. Social Cognitive Career Theory (SCCT): Conceptual Framework

Significant career development takes place during adolescence. Adolescents begin to clarify their career identity [2], develop an awareness of vocational interests and realities, and undertake career-related tasks, such as career planning and career exploration, as they increasingly think about their future career [3]. Social Cognitive Career Theory (SCCT) is a recent career theory that intends to unify common elements from previous career theorists, such as Super, Holland, Krumboltz, and Lofquist and Dawis, in order to create one framework to understand the (1) development of vocational interests, (2) making (and remaking) occupational choices, and (3) achievement of varying levels of career success and stability [4].

According to SCCT [4], three social cognitive variables play a significant role in vocational development: self-efficacy, outcome expectations, and goals [4, 5, 6]. SCCT has guided some of the inquiry on the pursuit (or avoidance) of science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) activities and academic majors. Findings indicate that individual SCCT variables, for instance, self-efficacy, are good predictors of STEM interests, goals, persistence, and performance [7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13] and most studies, have been focusing on women and minorities, given their underrepresentation in STEM fields [14].

The interests and goals influence Students' career choices through the development and interplay between the individual, environment, and behavior [4; Figure 1]. SCCT proposes that a wide range of individual and environmental factors contributes to a person's learning experiences that serve as a basis for developing self-efficacy and outcome expectations. According to Soldner, Rowan-Kenyon, Inkelas, Garvey, & Robbins [15, p. 314] self-efficacy are beliefs about one's own personal capabilities, which are hypothesized to affect academic and vocational decision-making by attenuating the judgments a student makes about his or her likelihood of surmounting obstacles that may lie in the path leading to attaining the desired career. Outcome expectations, or a person's anticipated results of performing one or more certain behaviors, shape vocational development differently [15, p. 314]. Positive future expectancies are hypothesized to motivate individuals to look past proximate situations, particularly challenging ones so that they can maintain focus on the attainment of long-term desires [15, p. 314]. These self-efficacy and outcome expectations, individually or in concert, lead to the generation of interests and goals. Goals are the intentions to engage in a given activity.

Then, according to Rogers and Creed [16, p. 163] “in turn, these social cognitive variables stimulate career choice actions (...) such as career planning and career exploration, which are necessary for the young person to make progress towards identified career goals”. Moreover, immediate environmental influences, such as social support and career barriers, can also affect self-efficacy’s influence on an individual’s interests, goals, and performance.

Figure 1: Model of social cognitive influences on career choice behavior [5].

Self-efficacy has been identified as a major influence on student performance and persistence (e.g., [17]). Among students in STEM programs self-efficacy beliefs have been found to influence academic performance (e.g., mathematics) and key indicators of academic motivation, including choice of activities and goals, persistence (e.g., graduation rates), and positive emotions [13, 18]. Self-efficacious students participate more readily, work harder, persist longer, and have fewer adverse reactions when encountering difficulty than students who doubt their capabilities [19]. Hackett and Betz [20] further proposed that self-efficacy has additional positive effects on educational and career decision-making, an assertion supported by research by findings from Multon, Brown, and Lent [20] showing self-efficacy to predict both college-major choices and academic performance. Consequently, in order to attract young talent to the aerospace sector we may ground in Lent, Brown, and Hackett’s [4, 5, 6] SCCT to examine the manner in which young people develop and elaborate on career and academic interests, select and pursue choices based on interests, and perform and persist in their occupational and educational pursuits on the aerospace sector.

3. Promoting youth occupational and educational pursuits in STEM and A&D sector – Build Awareness

3.1 Build awareness and spread information about STEM disciplines and aerospace occupations among young people

It is crucial to show young people how STEM skills can be applied to different occupations and attract employers. Therefore, promotion and awareness of STEM disciplines and aerospace occupations among young people and all community becomes a key factor when talking about attraction to the aerospace sector. Some practices can be:

- Awareness campaigns to enrich public understanding of career opportunities in Aerospace Sector and their nature, tasks, responsibilities, education needed, progression prospects, working conditions among others.
- Promote the sector aerospace sector as technological advanced, one of the most interdisciplinary branches of engineering, an enabler of a variety of vehicles and, finally, an opportunity to integrate all these technologies in a vehicle that is safe, efficient and environmentally friendly while allowing fast travel to a wide range of destinations, some previously inaccessible.

- Alert young people to the diversity of possible future career paths, requiring from 9th grade (e.g., baggage handler) to master's studies (e.g. Aviation Meteorologist Specialist) as education requirement for entry levels.
- Create strategies at school to involve families in STEM and in promoting positive attitudes to STEM and aerospace careers.
- Educate educators, such as teachers, career counsellors and other relevant educational bodies on how to promote student's persistence in STEM and on choosing aerospace careers, not only, but especially when finishing secondary school, because students have a wide and sometimes bewildering choice of university degrees to apply for and even restricting to STEM the options can be numerous and confusing;
- Promote the interaction of students with STEM and Aerospace professionals as role models, through testimonials sharing in school events, web-based presentations or others – this does not only builds awareness about the opportunities in STEM and Aerospace, as it also increases students' vicarious experience, one of the four sources of self-efficacy crucial for developing STEM interest and choice.
- “Career advice that includes images of people working in STEM-related careers, delivered through information workshops for careers teachers, and mathematics and science teachers” [22, p. 91] and
- “The inclusion, in curriculum resources, of images of people working in STEM-related careers” [22, p. 91] and specifically aerospace careers.

3.2 The importance of employer branding

The so-called war for talent, the intensified competition to attract the best employees to companies, arose motivated by the growing global competition and the mobilization of individuals for international markets, the rapid technological and demographic changes, as well as the clarification that human capital it is a source of value for organizations [23]. In this way, attracting and retaining talent has become one of the prominent challenges for the management of human resources, verifying that talent management, i.e., the systematic attraction, identification, development and retention of individuals with high potential, who are particular value for the organization [24], should focus on developing strategies to ensure that the talent pipeline remains adequate to the business challenges [25].

A strategy that could prove to be an effective weapon in this war for talent involves employer branding, the efforts made to communicate to current and potential employees that the organization is a desirable and distinctive workplace [26], integrating a long-term strategy that even allows managing the knowledge and perceptions of stakeholders [27]. In fact, characteristics such as culture, values, recruitment, remuneration, training and leadership have a strong impact on the employer brand that the organization builds [28], with positive repercussions in terms of attracting and retaining employees, attract talents, and also with regard to reducing recruitment costs, optimizing results [29] and increasing employee satisfaction and commitment [30], influencing individuals' perception of quality employment and the associated risk of being an integral part of the organization [31].

In this sense, the human resources of organizations must invest in a set of practices underlying a successful employer branding, namely defining the organization's profile, creating and maintaining a unique organizational culture, promoting a supportive culture, ensuring effective leadership [29], identifying talent needs, ensuring an efficient communication plan [31], promoting work-family balance, as well as training and integrating new employees [32], while also investing , in communicating with the outside through social media and holding open days in the organization. Nevertheless, it is crucial that there is consistency between these practices, not only to reflect the authenticity of the conceived image, but also so that there is coherence between internal and external employer branding, as positive experiences in employees enhance the effectiveness of external employer branding as a source of positive promotion of the organization's values and culture [31].

In short, currently, one of the biggest challenges is related to the attraction and retention of talent, which translates into costs for organizations that invest in the recruitment, training and development of employees who, therefore, tend to demonstrate high levels turnover. Thus, investing in employer branding may, in fact,

constitute an effective solution, seeking, however, to adapt this strategy to socio-economic conditions [33], since these generate different needs and, as such, distinct components of attractiveness for current and potential employees.

For instance, Airbus is investing in innovative recruitment practices, such as Twitter accounts to talk to potential recruits. Besides that, in 2014, EADS became the Airbus group, creating a unique and authentic employer brand, by using storytelling with the campaign "Make It Fly." Thus, Airbus uses storytelling as an employer branding strategy by presenting their own story through an infographic video and by a video for those who participated in the "Fly your ideas," a competition for the future aerospace workers, which indirectly shows their commitment to innovation and a culture of mentorship. This strong strategy placed Airbus as the 8th Most Attractive Employer across Europe and 1st in France.

Similarly, Rolls-Royce provides financial support to approximately 400 Ph.D. students, an innovative way to build a network of top talent. Of these, 25% of the graduates are recruited, with many more connections built [34].

This is particularly relevant in aeronautics, due to challenge of attracting young people and should be a main strategy of all HR departments all over the world.

4. Promoting youth occupational and educational pursuits in STEM and A&D sector – Human Resources Practices to Attract, Motivate & Retain

Human resources practices are recognized as important elements of business strategy development and they include, for example, recruitment and integration, employee involvement, internal communication, training and reward and commitment. Strategic human resource management theory asserts that these practices increase employees' knowledge, skills, and abilities (KSAs), empower employees to leverage their KSAs for organizational benefit, and increase their motivation to do so [35, 36]. The result is greater job satisfaction, lower employee turnover, higher productivity, and better decision making, all of which help improve organizational performance [37]. Therefore, this approach helps to accept and involve the HR function as a strategic factor in the formulation and implementation of the company's strategies, since human resource management capabilities are important for attracting young talent to an organization. Over the years, Human Resources Management (HRM) faced the requirement to adapt to new markets reality, work forms and workers' needs. Nowadays, it is necessary even a faster adaptation due to the constant market's demand change, technological developments, globalisation, and strong competition. Traditional and rigid forms of work organisation have proved that they are not efficient for motivating the workforce, which is a very important resource to achieve more efficiency and benefits, as employees work harder for the aims of the company they share. Therefore, the new challenge to be achieved will be to improve and adapt new HRM paradigms, by developing new methods to reward employees, in order to increase productivity and competitiveness in global markets. In relation to aviation sector, HRM becomes a key issue to assure its competitive position, since it is considered as one of the most innovative industries worldwide.

4.1 Organizational Culture

The study of culture has the particularity that there are numerous underlying meanings, the result of different approaches and theoretical perspectives related to the concept [38]. Although several definitions can be identified, in a more general way culture can be conceived as a set of values and practices defined and developed by the organization, on the basis of which a system of beliefs, norms and expectations that shape thought is socially built and the behavior of individuals [39, p.633].

Its conceptualization acquired consistency with the Schein model, which allowed a better understanding of the depth levels of the culture [40]. According to Schein [41], culture can be defined as the set of shared implicit assumptions that a group has and that determines the way it perceives, thinks and acts in relation to its various environments. Thus, this involves a learning process that has been carried out over time, as the

group has been solving its problems of external adaptation and internal integration and, therefore, is being transmitted to new members as the correct way to perceive, think and feeling about these problems [42]. According to [42], culture manifests itself at three distinct levels: observable artifacts, values and basic assumptions. At a more superficial level are Artefacts, which convey what can be seen and felt when an individual enters an organization, such as the physical environment, clothing, language and other manifestations of permanent dominance, such as records and annual reports. At an intermediate level, Values stand out, which reflect the organization's norms, ideologies, and philosophies and, therefore, define the desired objectives and behaviors. Finally, there are the Basic Assumptions, which constitute the core of the organizational culture and define the organizational context, insofar as they allow employees to understand how to direct their attention and the actions they must exhibit in different situations [38]. Thus, by constituting the interpretative framework of the company's reality, they allow employees to model their behavior [40].

Additionally, organizational culture has a solid influence on firm's innovativeness, a crucial factor in every aeronautics organization [43]. In today's contemporary business world, firms are under the great pressure of highly competitive and global markets. For aeronautics companies it is highly critical to become innovative and differentiate themselves to act as a key piece on this complex and competitive environment. By creating and sustaining an organizational culture that nurtures creative efforts and facilitates diffusion of learning, leaders can significantly boost organizational creativity [44]. Also, organizations can develop and maintain a system that values and rewards creative performance through compensation. When exists a way to reward intrinsically and extrinsically the efforts to make a creative work, organizations can take an advantage of the motivation of employees to be creative and learn new skills.

To sum up, maintaining a good organizational culture is one strategy to allow companies to evolve in this competitive times and markets. So, the identification of key variables related to innovativeness and the process to construct a good and solid organizational culture should be a top priority to aeronautics companies in order to improve their results and sustainability. Therefore, is important to point out that organizational culture acts as a form of attracting and motivating the workforce and can constitute an important Human Resource strategy.

4.2. Satisfaction of Employees

Employees satisfaction is a measure of how happy workers are with their job and working environment and can be seen as an emotional state that result from the evaluation of one's job or experience.

In the journey of the consolidation of a company, employees and collaborators have a key role cooperating for the same goal. In a job environment it is usual that some employees are dissatisfied with their work due to the fact that their conditions in the company are not optimal, so they end up leaving the company which causes a constant rotation in the organizations. Clearly this is a negative point for the company due to it generates distrust and instability besides it increases the costs in the search and recruiting of new personnel and creates a negative image about the company and the sector. Thus, keeping the employees is an essential requirement in order to make the company successful and to attract young people effectively.

If a company provide the employees with an environment where schedule changes and other facilities are possible, employees will be willing to stay working for the firm as they feel comprehension and empathy from the company.

Also, it is undeniable that employees are the company's best advertising, for public in general, and for prospective applicants.

In fact, and in accordance with the previous information, having good relationships with the colleagues, high salary, good working conditions, training and education opportunities, career developments or any other benefits may be related with the increasing of employee satisfaction and consequently with the attraction of new personnel.

In order to enrich the levels of employee satisfaction, some changes can be made [45]:

- Organizational Development, in order to implement effective change in an organizational.
- Policies of Compensation and Benefit, because it is important that employees are satisfied with the salary package and a feel of satisfaction is achieved by attaining fair rewards.
- Promotion and Career Development.

- Job Satisfaction, and the importance of the nature of the work itself, often called “intrinsic job characteristics” (job challenge, autonomy, variety) that should be as interesting and challenging as possible [46].
- Job Security, that consists in the assurance or confidence that the employee will keep their current job.
- Working Environment and Condition: it is essential to have good conditions, as feeling safe and comfort, have good tools and equipment, have good working methods, etc.
- Good relationship with Supervisor.
- Work Group, i.e., people like to interact with others and the existence of group in organizations it is an important factor.
- Leadership Styles, where it is preferable to choose a democratic style of leadership in order to have a friendship, respect and warmth relationship.

But why should organizations make all this investment? Along the time, various studies have been showing that employee satisfaction is positively correlated with motivation, job involvement, organizational citizenship behaviour, organizational commitment, life satisfaction, mental health, and job performance, and negatively related to absenteeism, turnover, and perceived stress.

Also, and as previously mentioned, studies and theories prove that it is not only about who work there, but who might will. In fact, firms' corporate social performance (CSP) is related positively to their reputations and to their attractiveness as employers [47]. More, in the aviation sector, factors such as innovativeness are especially important and in order to secure future innovation, growth and competitiveness companies must be attractive for potential employees. Consequently, innovative companies might be at an advantage as they appear more attractive to employees in general organizations, revealing that a strong innovation culture appear to be an important way to attract potential employees [48].

In conclusion, are this kind of practices, with focus on employee and their well-being, that assure the satisfaction, happiness, and loyalty [46], that is exactly the way we can attract new personnel, retain workers and guarantee the stability of the workforce.

4.3. Stability of the Workforce

Employee fidelity can be defined as employees who are devoted to the success of their organization and believe that being an employee of this organization is in their best interest. Not only do they plan to remain with the organization, but they do not actively seek for alternative employment opportunities.

What is identified in US as a “mobility problem” is a combination of the behavioural loyalty (the perception of the shortage in the labour market) and the Peter Principle (promotion of a person until it reaches its level if incompetence). A favouriting factor in this approach in US is the huge size of the workforce in Aerospace: over 700 000 people employed, compared with about 400 000 in Europe and nearly the same figure in China. The average productivity (sales per employee) in Japan Aerospace industry is higher (12%) than its US counterpart [49].

Workforce issues in aerospace are near the top of the list of challenges facing the industry. A significant number of workers in aerospace are eligible for retirement or approaching retirement eligibility in the next five years. Unfortunately, the uncertainty of workforce retirement makes it difficult to plan for the future. Regardless of these issues, companies must ensure they maintain current expertise while forecasting future hiring needs, such as what skill sets will be needed and when to hire for them.

In the fight for talent, aerospace companies face industry-specific challenges. To recruit and retain talent, especially people with the STEM (Scientific, Technical, Engineering, Maths) skills that are so highly prized in many different industries (with critical skills for today and emerging skill requirements for the future). It is currently considered of great importance how best to ensure the transfer of talent from older to younger employees, an issue that is becoming more acute as the older employees retire. They have a relatively high proportion of older workers (approximately 60% of aerospace employees are over age 45 vs. 44% in the overall US workforce. Conversely, approximately 42% of aerospace employees is under age 44 vs. 56% in the overall workforce).

This lopsided demographic mix, coupled with high attrition rates and increased labour mobility, poses serious risks to the industry. Companies can mitigate the risks with employee retention and succession planning. But as retirement rates creep up, it is increasingly important to approach the issue of succession in a systematic way that includes leaders and management as well as critical technical employees.

The loyalty of the workforce in an aerospace organization is a very important ingredient in the quality of the output. The first determinant is pay. The average hourly wages in aerospace industry, at \$45 (compared with \$30 in automotive industry and \$28 in manufacturing overall), is surpassed only by the \$46 in coal and petroleum. However, such a very meagre gain in pay in the extractive industries is not attractive when the working conditions are considered. The working conditions are the second determinant. And an “esprit de corps” (a feeling of pride and mutual loyalty) is probably the third. This happy combination makes employment in aerospace desirable and competitive within the labour market. What would further enhance the fidelity of the employees? Obviously, a perceived high job security (a reduced risk of being made redundant), a good and reliable pension system, an effective health insurance scheme and an optional extension of the retirement age could only increase the attractiveness and the excitement of the employment in aerospace and retain talent, especially people with the STEM skills.

In conclusion, retaining the workforce should be a top priority for the aeronautics because the intention of the workforce to leave the organization and the withdrawal itself can have a domino effect on other human resource concerns as the quality of the service, productivity and the success of the sector in general, affecting the future attractiveness of young people to Aeronautics [50].

5. Conclusion

To promote youth occupational and educational pursuits in STEM and A&D sector and having in consideration the SSCT national and European agendas should create policies that focus on promoting contextual support for STEM disciplines and aerospace occupations, because perceived career supports from family, school community members, classmates, and role models have particularly strong associations with engineering and STEM self-efficacy.

In addition, building awareness of STEM disciplines and A&D occupations among youth and employer branding of A&D companies are essential factors to take into consideration when talking about promoting STEM and, specifically, A&D occupations.

The challenge of STEM means that there are proportionally fewer candidates than for soft skills and services. This makes the STEM able professionals the key actors of the future prosperity of the aerospace sector in Europe. Therefore, having Human Resources practices in favor of the organizations and the sector, is an excellence strategy because, on one hand we help to develop the sector and the conditions of actual workers and, on another hand, we ensure that aerospace remains a good option for young talent and future workforce.

To sum up, in order to attract young talent to the aerospace, it is important to analyze the context and the influences since an early age (Social Cognitive Career Theory, SCCT) and, therefore, reorganize the organizational context. Some strategies are mentioned and should be implemented in organizations.

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